

Field observations and repeated breeding of the Spectacled Salamander, *Salamandrina terdigitata*

Sergé Bogaerts & Frank Pasmans
c/o Honigbijenhof 3
NL-6533 RW Nijmegen
The Netherlands
s.bogaerts@hetnet.nl

Habitat of *Salamandrina terdigitata*, near Uscio.

Photo's: S. Bogaerts unless otherwise indicated.

INTRODUCTION

In 1996 the first author obtained ten captive-bred Spectacled Salamanders (*Salamandrina terdigitata*), which were raised in an outdoor enclosure. In the same period, the second author received nine recently metamorphosed animals, with an average length of 19 mm, from an acquaintance. Rearing these very small salamanders turned out to be a difficult matter. By the end of 1999, the animals of the second author had all died and the first author only had two animals left. They turned out to be a pair, and these two animals reproduced in 2000. In 2002, a second successful breeding occurred. Since little information on this interesting little salamander exists in the terrarium literature (only MISSLER (1996) and SCHULTSCHIK (2001) briefly report on their experiences), we present here our adventures with this species in captivity, complemented by our observations in the wild.

Salamandrina terdigitata, in the wild.

DISTRIBUTION AND HABITAT

The Spectacled Salamander, *Salamandrina terdigitata*, is a species that is only found in Italy, roughly west of the Apennines. It lives along deeply shaded, slow-moving clear streams, often in steep ravines covered in deciduous forest and with a high relative humidity. Usually these valleys are oriented towards the north, north-west, or north-east (ZUFFI, 1999). This salamander reaches an average total length of 8-9 cm (ZUFFI, 1999), more than half of that is taken up by the tail. In Campania (southern Italy) these animals remain considerably smaller, with an average total length of 6.5 cm (PASMANS & DRIESKENS, 2002).

MALE OR FEMALE?

It is very difficult to determine the sex of these salamanders, especially when one is accustomed to examining the shape of the cloaca or the ornamentations on males. In Spectacled Salamanders it is more important to look at relative sizes. Males generally have a longer tail than females but, more importantly, have a much more slender stature and larger head (ZUFFI, 1999). The gravid females in particular are abnormally plump for such a skinny-looking salamander.

FIELD OBSERVATIONS

Eggs of *Salamandrina terdigitata* in the wild.

In May/June of 2000 we had our first opportunity to observe the habitat of these animals east of Genoa. It quickly became clear that the eggs of Spectacled Salamanders are not deposited until May here. We only found recently deposited eggs and no larvae. Eggs of *Salamandrina terdigitata* were found in three types of aquatic habitats. South of Boasi they were in small brooks with slowly trickling water and small puddles with an average diameter of 50 cm. Near one of these puddles was a concrete washbasin that was being used by the salamanders as well. Here they used the water from a small branch of the main stream. It contained eggs, but also many larvae of the

Spectacled Salamander. In the same habitat we also discovered Cave Salamanders, *Speleomantes strinatii*. Eggs of the Spectacled Salamander were also found in a tributary of a somewhat larger brook near Uscio. It was striking that here the larvae of *Salamandra salamandra* (subspecies *gigliolii*?) were nearly all at the point of metamorphosis or had already left the water.

	Location	Water temperature	Air temperature	Humidity	Hardness of water	Acidity of water
Trickling stream with puddles	Boasi	14°C	20°C	74%	DH 9	pH 8
Brook	Uscio	14°C	18°C	69%	DH 7	pH 8

Table: Data on two bodies of water where eggs of *Salamandrina terdigitata* were found.

In Central Italy one can expect to find eggs from late fall (November) to late spring (May) (CORSETTI, 1999). In Campania (southern Italy) it appears that eggs are deposited starting early fall (PASMANS & DRIESKENS, 2002).

Despite elaborate nocturnal searches and turning over tons of rock, we were only able to uncover two adult animals; the first animal (a male) was found under a small rock, while the second (a female) was located under a rock along the banks of a stream.

BEHAVIOUR

The behaviour of this salamander is still poorly known. Their activity is mostly limited to the small hours of the night, preferably during rain or when a high relative humidity prevails. On humid, rainy days during spring or in the fall, these animals are also active in the early morning or late afternoon (ZUFFI, 1999).

Their reproductive behaviour is also still a matter of speculation. The only thing known so far is based on an observation from 1927 (!). During this incident, which took place in December, a captive male was observed to approach a female on land and touch her cloacal region with his snout, which initiated a kind of circular courtship dance. Subsequently, the male stopped abruptly and deposited a two mm high spermatophore that was accepted by the female. No amplexus took place (STRÖTGEN (1927) in THORN, 1968). In the terrarium it is also very difficult to observe this and other behaviours since these animals live a very secretive life. Even at night they are rarely seen. Therefore, these salamanders are not suited for terrarium hobbyists who would like to observe their animals every day.

The Spectacled Salamander on very few occasions displays a typical defensive behaviour (the first author has only observed this once in a juvenile animal). The tail is arched forward over the back, thus displaying its bright red underside (LANZA, 1967). Captive-bred animals tend to have a more orange belly and tail.

THE TERRARIUM

The animals of the first author have been housed in a small aquarium (30x15x20 (lwxh) cm) since they were purchased. The aquarium contains 2-5 cm of water and shards of pottery, rocks, bark, and pieces of peat are stacked to the very top of the container. A plate of glass, opened to a very small crack to enable air circulation, covers the aquarium. This ensures that the relative humidity inside remains very high. Moss and small ferns make up the vegetation inside the terrarium. The water contains some *Vesicularia duyana* and *Elodea* sp. From the start, the terrarium has been located in a 'cold' room where the temperature fluctuates around 5°C during the winter and 20-25°C in the summer. The second author has only kept his animals in an outdoor enclosure.

FOOD

These small salamanders 'shoot' their prey with their tongue. Therefore, one should provide them with mostly small, rapidly moving prey animals. We usually feed them large and small fruit flies, complemented with small crickets, springtails, and sometimes aphids. Larvae are fed daphnia, tubifex, and red mosquito larvae. Metamorphs predominantly feed

on springtails. They were also offered mites (which had developed in the fruit fly colony) but these seemed to bother the salamanders more than actually feed them. The juvenile salamanders were also fed aphids. STEINFARTZ (1995) indicated that these animals should be fed large quantities of food, more so than any other salamander of comparable size.

BREEDING

In 1999, the first author only had two animals left of the original group of ten. From the beginning of that year onwards, the animals were kept slightly warmer (15-20°C) and the terrarium was sprayed more frequently during fall and winter (1999-2000). The female had clearly become plumper during the fall of 1999, but no mating was ever observed. The female measured roughly 70 mm in total length (32+38 mm snout-vent + tail).

On January 25, 2000 the author discovered eggs in the water. They were not stuck together in small clumps but attached individually to plants and rocks. It was not easy to count them since several were deposited between rocks, but there were probably about 25-35 in total. They were already fairly well developed and it is possible that they had been deposited several days earlier. The white larvae were already clearly visible inside the eggs. The water temperature fluctuated around 15°C and the water level was raised to 5 cm. The eggs were left in the terrarium for fear of possibly damaging or disturbing them upon removal. The water compartment of the terrarium was not equipped with a pump or air filter.

On February 13, seven larvae hatched. On February 28, the larvae had already developed four legs. On March 27, there were about 20 larvae visible at night. The larvae were clearly bottom-dwellers, not aggressive towards each other, and mostly nocturnal. On April 7, a recently metamorphosed animal was discovered that had drowned. From that moment on, each larva that was about to go through metamorphosis (which can be determined based on the darkening of the back and the appearance of the "spectacles" on the head) was transferred to a separate aquarium with very little water and many aquatic plants. In addition, the water level in the main aquarium was reduced to two cm. The first larva metamorphosed after ten weeks.

REARING THE YOUNG

Between April 7 and 27 of 2000, a total of 27 salamanders metamorphosed at the first author's home. Several individuals were measured and were all 12+13 mm in length (snout-vent + tail). In 2002, the largest of the metamorphs in the second clutch measured no less than 13+18 mm. The metamorphs that the second author received in 1997 on average measured only 19 mm in total length.

During May and June of 2000 the juveniles of the first author were reared indoors in small plastic containers decorated with small pieces of moist peat, bark and forest soil. They were mostly fed aphids. Partially because of a three-week vacation, the first author decided to house his offspring outdoors in an old aquarium (80x40x40 cm) that had the bottom removed. It was placed in a shaded part of the garden and buried about 10 cm deep. In the centre, blocks of waterlogged peat were stacked, as well as pieces of bark. On July 12, 2000 all 25 remaining juveniles were transferred to this outdoor enclosure. In one of the corners of the aquarium some rotting fruit was placed to attract insects and other prey animals. After three weeks 15 juveniles were returned inside, while 10 others remained outside. The fifteen juvenile *Salamandrina terdigitata* were

Juvenile *Salamandrina terdigitata*, with a paperclip for size comparison.

maintained in the plastic containers again, but unfortunately these animals did not do well. One after the other died. On September 17 the other animals located outside were recaptured. Nine remained, the larger of which measured 35 mm in total length. Only two animals from the group that was maintained inside survived. On October 8 only nine juveniles remained which were placed with their parents in an indoor terrarium. In March of 2001 eight were still alive.

At that time, the second author successfully raised nine juvenile *Salamandrina terdigitata* in an outdoor enclosure. This enclosure consisted of a large, old plastic tray with most of the bottom cut out. The tray was buried upside down in the soil. The sides of the deep tray were tapering inwards, and the remaining, inward-facing edges of the bottom further helped to prevent the animals from escaping. This enclosure was filled with pieces of bark, branches, and leaf litter. In this tray the nine animals successfully hibernated. After one year, the juveniles had grown from 19 mm to an average of 55 mm in total length. Consecutively, the animals were further reared indoors in a small terrarium measuring 40x20x20 cm, located in a cool salamander room with a minimum winter temperature of 10°C and a maximum summer temperature of 23°C. The bottom substrate consists of somewhat humid, leafy soil. Pieces of bark were stacked on top. This system appeared to work fine for eight months. However, in July of 1999 all animals died within a week, at an average total length of 66 mm. Among the symptoms observed were: weight loss, lack of appetite, and muscular weakness; in short, a rapid decline (cachexia), a matt sheen on the skin, and the development of clumps on fingers and toes. Death eventually came through blood poisoning (septicaemia). Several bacteria were isolated from the deceased animals, including *Aeromonas* sp.

Larval *Salamandrina terdigitata* in captivity.

Five juveniles from the first batch of offspring, born in 2000, were donated to other salamander hobbyists. The three animals that remained with the first author unfortunately died in the spring of 2002 at a total length of approximately five centimetres. Dave Herbert (Brandon, Suffolk, England) has been able to keep three animals alive up until now. He maintains his animals in plastic boxes (17x17x8 cm), housing two salamanders per box. The bottom substrate consists of humid (not moist) tissue paper with a small piece of bark for a hiding place. The salamanders are only fed crickets, varying in size from hatchlings to several-day old ones. These are dusted with a calcium supplement used for horses (Equimins Limestone Flour). Once every two weeks the crickets are dusted with a reptilian vitamin supplement (Repton). The salamanders are fed twice weekly and the boxes are cleaned every week. From now on the first author is going to apply this technique as well.

DISCUSSION

Field observations

From our own field observations east of Genoa we concluded that the eggs are only deposited in May. We did not encounter any larvae. We did find large, metamorphosing larvae of *Salamandra salamandra*. These larvae were clearly deposited in early spring. Possibly there is some relationship between these two species of salamander. Perhaps *Salamandrina terdigitata* attempts to minimise the chances of predation by the much larger and more predacious larvae of *Salamandra salamandra* by depositing the eggs later in the season?

There are substantial regional differences in the timing of oviposition, which possibly are related to climate changes (for example, the time when streams fill with water). In northern Italy eggs are deposited in late spring (personal observations). In central Italy, eggs of *Salamandrina terdigitata* are found from November until far into May (CORSETTI, 1999). In Campania (southern Italy) it appears that the eggs of *Salamandrina terdigitata* are deposited even earlier: at least as early as the onset of October (PASMANS & DRIESKENS, 2002).

Only south of Boasi we have found small larvae in May/June. However, the larvae of *Salamandrina terdigitata* are tiny, fast, and hide at the least sign of disturbance. In addition, the animals are photophobic, making it near impossible to find them during the day.

Salamandrina terdigitata, from Campania.

Photo: F. Pasmans

Keeping and rearing in a terrarium

The manner in which we maintain our salamanders in an indoor terrarium differs little from that of other authors. MISSLER (1996) kept a group of two males and four females in a container measuring 40x25x25 cm. The temperature would drop to 8°C in the winter and during the summer it would rise to an average of 23°C. STEINFARTZ (1995) also reports that his Spectacled Salamanders can easily sustain such relatively high summer temperatures. STEINFARTZ (1995) kept ten animals in a terrarium measuring roughly 80x30x40 cm with a 5-6 cm deep water level. Flat rocks were placed in the water and covered with moss and bark.

In general, rearing the juveniles outside resulted in far less casualties than when they were raised indoors. The animals grew to a total length of 55 mm within a year, approximately

15 mm less than the size of sexually mature salamanders (ZUFFI, 1999). The difference is most likely caused by the lack of variation in the small prey animals that can be offered indoors. In addition, the loss of animals to invertebrate predators (spiders and centipedes) outside appears to be very limited, as indicated by the fact that hardly any of the tiny metamorphs died in spite of the presence of, e.g. wolf spiders (Lycosidae). One disadvantage of the outdoor system is that there is no way of controlling environmental factors. During prolonged wet periods, for example, an outdoor enclosure can become too wet which may damage the animals. The second author, who raised 18 juveniles in an outdoor enclosure for a period of two years, had this experience. After a three-week rainy period, no salamanders were recovered.

Female *Salamandrina terdigitata*, responsible for all captive offspring.

Breeding

Although no mating attempts have been observed, fertilised eggs were found by the end of January 2000, produced by the only pair remaining with the first author. These animals were four years old by then. MISSLER (1996) also reports his suspicion that these animals do not reach sexual maturity until the age of four.

The size of this female (70 mm) appears to be the smallest ever reported for a breeding female, when compared with the data supplied by ZUFFI (1999). The number of eggs deposited on both occasions was estimated to be about 25-30. MISSLER (1996) reported that he frequently found eggs, 10-18 on average per female. This number is significantly lower than that of the aforementioned much smaller female. ZUFFI (1999) mentions that clutch size in nature can be up to 40-60 per female. Considering the data presented above, we suspect that Missler only had one or two out of his four females laying eggs, which leads to a much lower average per female.

According to CORSETTI (1999) the hatching of the eggs may occur between 23-28 days (at a water temperature of 13.5-16.5°C) to approximately 42 days (at water temperatures of 11-12°C). The eggs found by the first author hatched 20 days after discovery at a temperature of 15-20°C. This is why we suspect that the eggs were merely days old when they were discovered. The larvae measured 10-12 mm upon hatching; comparable to the

values indicated by MISSLER (1996). ZUFFI (1999) reported 7-12 mm larval size upon hatching.

At metamorphosis in 2000, some individuals were measured and those all reached 12+13 mm (snout-vent + tail); 25 mm in total length. In 2002, the largest metamorph measured 13+18 mm; 31 mm in total length. The recently metamorphosed animals received by the second author measured 19 mm total length on average. MISSLER'S (1996) animals measured 28-35 mm upon metamorphosis; ZUFFI (1999) indicated a size of 22-30 mm. The 19 mm animals were thus extremely small upon purchase. It is not known how they were reared as larvae.

Breeder	Time until hatching and incubation temperature	Average total length upon hatching (mm)	Time until metamorphosis and temperature	Average total length at metamorphosis (mm)
S. Bogaerts (first author)	3 weeks (15-20°C)	10-12	10 weeks (72 days) (15-20°C)	25 (in 2000) 25-31 (in 2002)
MISSLER (1996)	3 weeks (18-20 °C)	10-12	8-10 weeks (18-20°C)	28-35
CORSETTI (1999)	3-4 weeks (13.5-16.5°C) 6 weeks (11-12°C)	-	-	-
ZUFFI (1999)	-	7-12	10-20 weeks	22-30

Table: Data on breeding of *Salamandrina terdigitata*.

Metamorphosis started approximately 10 weeks after oviposition. MISSLER (1996) reported 8 to 10 weeks for this period when the larvae were kept at room temperature. SCHULTSCHIK (2001) indicated that the first larvae metamorphosed after 57 days (at a water temperature of 15°C). ZUFFI (1999) reported that in nature metamorphosis commences after two months and may take up to five months, depending on the water temperature.

Our experiences unfortunately indicate that metamorphosing *Salamandrina terdigitata* drown very easily, in spite of a very low water level and the presence of sufficient rocks to help them climb out of the water. As soon as an animal reaches metamorphosis (after approximately ten weeks in our collections), it needs to be transferred separately to a container with a very low water level and many small aquatic plants.

Rearing the young

Recently metamorphosed *Salamandrina terdigitata*.

Juvenile *Salamandrina terdigitata*, at the age of six months.

These animals grow fairly slowly, as opposed to newts of the genus *Triturus*, for example. These latter newts can almost double their size in one year and may reproduce in their first Spring (e.g. BOGAERTS, 1997; 2002). *Salamandrina terdigitata* reach sexual maturity after four years at the earliest. The animals of the second author reached 55 mm total length after one year in his outdoor enclosure. In nature they would measure 35-40 mm by that time (ZUFFI, 1999). If this growth curve would have continued the animals could theoretically reach adulthood after 2-3 years. This could perhaps be attempted sometime. Rearing the young has been the biggest problem so far. An outdoor enclosure with a varied diet and the right environmental conditions seems to allow for a successful development, although a sterile approach appears to work as well. All intermediate conditions have not proven to be successful yet. Finding the right food in combination with the proper husbandry conditions (humidity, temperature, etc.) is the biggest challenge now. Hopefully we will someday be able to publish a successful formula for that.

CONCLUSIONS

Keeping the adult animals appears to be relatively easy as long as one offers sufficient variation in the dry and wet climatic conditions inside the terrarium and provides the animals with high quality food. The terrarium does not need to be large. Rearing the young also appears relatively easy. There is no mutual aggression and the larva can be fed tubifex and daphnia. No special water conditions are required. However, juveniles are hard to maintain. The results in outdoor enclosures and the sterile method of Dave Herbert's indoor terrarium have turned out the best results so far.

IN CONCLUSION

When considering that females weigh about 2.5 grams before oviposition and a mere 1.3 grams after (VANNI, 1980), it is obvious that this is a very energetically costly activity. A

long period of recuperation will be necessary. Therefore, we suspect that females will only reproduce once every 2-3 years. This was definitely the case with the female that has deposited eggs twice now at the first author's home.

In the same year that there was a successful breeding attempt by the first author, Günther Schultschik from Austria also succeeded in breeding these animals (SCHULTSCHIK, 2001). He had 74 animals that made it through metamorphosis, but subsequently lost them all. After discussing this problem we came to the conclusion that an important difference in our ways of maintaining these animals lay in the food: we feed our animals aphids.

These salamanders remain very special to us, as there is a still lot of new information to be gained e.g., their courtship behaviour still remains unknown. We hope that this article contributes to the enthusiasm of other keepers of these animals, encouraging them to experiment with finding new ways to successfully breed this species. This could eventually lead to the continued survival of this species as a hobby animal. These salamanders are strictly protected by the EU habitat guidelines, which preclude any legal import of wild-caught animals.

Ventral view of a male *Salamandrina terdigitata* in captivity.

SUMMARY

We describe experiences with the raising, keeping, and breeding of the Spectacled Salamander, *Salamandrina terdigitata*. This species is endemic to the western part of the Apennine Mountains in Italy where it lives among heavily shaded streams with a high humidity. Adult salamanders grow to a maximum of 9 cm. We also report on observations in the field. Data on the water quality of the breeding habitats are given. Animals were kept in different ways, varying from very small aquaria indoors to outdoor enclosures. These salamanders were fed fruit flies, small crickets, springtails, and occasionally aphids. Data are given on two successful breedings by one of the authors. Our findings seem to indicate that females reproduce only every other year. Raising larvae was easy, whereas raising juveniles was extremely difficult.

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